

Frame by frame, attitude by attitude – The effect of information framing in videos on consumers' acceptance of sustainable food production innovations

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ABSTRACT

Innovations in the agricultural sector were identified as key drivers for the transition towards more sustainable food production. To achieve consumer acceptance, it is necessary to communicate about innovations and sustainable food production processes effectively. This study investigates the effect of loss- and gain-framing on consumers' implicit and explicit attitudes towards, and purchase intentions of, agricultural innovations, using the example of beneficial soil-microbes in tomato production. We conducted a pre-registered, online, experimental study with a between-subjects design among German consumers ($n = 754$). To test the effect of communication, three video clips were created: a control video, a loss-frame video and a gain-frame video. The control video described the innovation on a technical level without specific framing. Through the usage of videos, visual and linguistic framing cues could be applied. Group comparisons of the different types of framing did not result in significant differences. Results of a serial mediation analysis show that explicit attitudes play an important role in the model. The effect of both loss- and gain-framing in relation to the control video resulted in a significant effect on explicit attitudes, and these in turn had a significant effect on purchase intentions. Findings from this study suggest that information videos that describe the consequences of innovation application (loss- or gain-framing) contribute more strongly towards innovation acceptance than more technical and neutral accounts (our control video) of the innovation.

1. Introduction

With the 'Farm-to-Fork-strategy' in the European Green Deal, the European Union (EU) made the agri-food sector one of the cornerstones in the transition towards a healthier and more sustainable EU (European Commission, 2019). Innovations can be key in this process. They are crucial e.g. in efforts to accelerate the route towards an agriculture less dependent on hazardous pesticides and inorganic fertilisers (European Union, 2020). In this respect, beneficial soil-microbes, such as bacteria or fungi, are considered a promising while sustainable innovative contribution (Singh et al., 2011). Beneficial soil-microbes have the potential to enhance the plants' health and resilience, thereby increasing crop yield and quality while reducing the dependence on agrochemicals, and thereby contributing to sustainable food production. This possibility of microbial applications in commercial agriculture to specifically support sustainable food production has been identified by several researchers (Hamid et al., 2021; Rouphael & Colla, 2020).

Societal acceptance of innovations is a critical factor for the success of a transition towards a more sustainable food system. Early dialogue with respect to new food production methods can enhance public awareness, allows for an informed choice, and can help to overcome the 'farm-to-table knowledge gap' (Jeong & Lundy, 2015; Sutherland et al., 2020). It also provides a promising avenue to prevent confusion, scepticism and open resistance with regard to technologies, as in the case of genetically modified (GM) food (Hess et al., 2016).

The communication format and media used for presenting information can play a decisive role in gaining consumers' attention (Perrin, 2011), and thus influencing technology acceptance. There is increasing evidence that videos are a suitable communication medium to inform consumers about a range of complex topics; such as, climate change (Goldberg et al., 2019), sustainable animal-husbandry systems (Risius & Hamm, 2017) or obesity prevention (Cheung et al., 2017), where videos have been shown to be more successful than text material (e.g. Cheung et al., 2017; Goldberg et al., 2019) in influencing attitudes and

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behaviour. Message framing has been shown to be an effective technique to inform people and motivate behaviour change (Li & Su, 2018). Information framing entails communication that is based on the selection of specific content and on making this particularly salient (Entman, 1993). A common type of framing is the so-called goal-framing (Levin et al., 1998). In this respect messages can emphasise the expected benefits of a specific behaviour (gain-frame) or the possible loss if a specific behaviour is not followed (loss-frame; Rothman & Salovey, 1997). Using this method, information presenting an innovation can emphasise the positive outcomes associated with introducing an innovation (i.e., a gain-frame) or the negative outcomes if that innovation is not adopted (i.e., a loss-frame).

The objective of the present study is to investigate the effect of information framing in videos on consumer acceptance of an agricultural innovation. More specifically, we focus on beneficial soil-microbes in tomato production and investigate the effect of gain- and loss-framing in videos on consumers' explicit and implicit attitudes towards and purchase intention of tomatoes produced using this technology. We extend previous research twofold: First, we investigate the effects that loss- and gain-framing may have not only on explicit but also on implicit attitudes. Second, we apply goal-framing using video clips, as a mode for communication. To the best of our knowledge, this has hardly been employed in the framing literature and is lacking with respect to agricultural and food innovations.

2. Literature review

2.1. The relevance of attitudes and intentions

If consumers will adopt a new technology, adoption behaviour can be predicted by their attitude and behavioural intentions (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2010; Kamrath et al., 2019). While the attitude expresses the degree of favour with which consumers evaluate a technology (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993), behavioural intentions indicate whether consumers plan to adopt the technology in the future. According to the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), a positive attitude towards adopting innovations causally leads to increased behavioural intentions to adopt the technology (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2010).

An attitude has different facets and can be distinguished in explicit and implicit attitudes. Explicit attitudes are deliberate, conscious evaluations that can be assessed through self-reported measures (Greenwald & Banaji, 1995). In contrast, implicit attitudes are automatic, spontaneous evaluations that cannot be consciously reported by consumers (Gawronski & Bodenhausen, 2006). Instead, researchers use response-time tests which allow to draw inferences about the underlying implicit attitude. A common method is the implicit association test (IAT) (Greenwald, McGhee, & Schwartz, 1998; Greenwald & Lai, 2020). Response-time measures are less prone to potential biases of self-report measures, such as social desirability (van de Mortel, 2008). Therefore, the inclusion of an implicit attitude measure allows for a more holistic representation of consumers' attitude, compared to an explicit measure only. An example of the use of implicit and explicit attitude measures in the domain of agricultural food production, specifically regarding different cop protection methods, is provided by Römer and colleagues. They found an explicit-implicit attitude gap and conclude that studies of attitudes towards agricultural production methods would lack potential explanation possibilities without the inclusion of implicit attitudes (Römer et al., 2019). Although this study did not include a measure of behavioural intentions, other research has shown that both implicit and explicit attitudes serve as predictors for behavioural intentions (Baum et al., 2021; Perugini, 2005; Ratliff et al., 2017), which is in line with the TPB (Ajzen, 1991).

According to the associative-propositional evaluation (APE) model, communication can influence both implicit and explicit attitudes (Gawronski & Bodenhausen, 2006). Empirical support for this notion is offered by several studies (e.g., Ackermann et al., 2018; Baum et al.,

2021; Weingarten & Hartmann, 2023; Whitfield & Jordan, 2009). Furthermore, attitudes are not only directly influenced by information, but implicit and explicit attitudes also mutually influence each other. As shown by Weingarten and Hartmann (2023), explicit attitudes fully mediated the effect of information provision on implicit attitudes, whereas implicit attitudes only partly mediated the effect of information provision on explicit attitudes. Moreover, consistent with the TPB, if communication affects attitudes this should also influence behavioural intentions (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2010). Therefore, we test whether communication serially influences explicit attitudes, implicit attitudes, and intentions.

2.2. The effect of loss- and gain-framing

There are various ways how information can be framed when communication is targeting consumers. According to prospect theory, consumers are more sensitive to potential losses than to potential gains of a decision or action, as consumers place more weight on losses than gains (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). Thus, information outlining potential losses of a specific behaviour is assumed to impact consumers' attitude and intention more strongly, compared to the description of potential gains when abstaining from that behaviour (O'Keefe & Jensen, 2006). In the literature, this kind of goal-framing is referred to as loss- and gain-framing (Homar & Cvelbar, 2021; Levin et al., 1998).

The superiority of loss-frames might be due to the depth with which consumers deal with loss-versus gain-related information. According to the elaboration likelihood model (ELM; Petty & Cacioppo, 1986), information can be processed via two different routes. The first route is the peripheral route involving superficial message processing, which is associated with a weak attitude change. Alternatively, information can be processed via the central route; this route involves the systematic in-depth processing of information, which is associated with stronger attitude changes (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986). Whether the first or second route is used for information processing depends on a number of conditions, such as the perceived relevance of the message. It can be assumed that loss-framed messages will induce stronger central route processing than gain-framed messages. According to O'Keefe and Jensen (2008) this could be the case because: (1) of the threat perception communicated in a loss-frame and (2) of the required reaction to avert this threat. In a systematic review on information framing related to environmental decisions, the authors demonstrate that loss-framing is more effective (Homar & Cvelbar, 2021).

Previous research demonstrated how goal-framing can be applied in the context of specific agricultural production conditions. For example, Britwum and Yiannaka (2019) evaluated loss- and gain-frames in a choice experiment regarding preferences for cattle treatments against infections. In line with other studies, the authors demonstrated that loss-frames led to a higher willingness-to-pay compared to gain-frames. Or for the case of GM vegetables, negative framing impacted its' perceptions more than positive framing (Heiman & Zilberman, 2011). In the case of products produced with/without genetical modification and antibiotics recall effects were stronger for the loss group than for the gain group (Jeong & Lundy, 2015). Theoretical insights and the majority of empirical research generally suggest a superiority of loss-frames (Homar & Cvelbar, 2021), however, some researchers obtained deviating results. For example, research on organic seafood showed that positive framing increased purchase intentions (Cucchiara et al., 2015). No differences between framing could be detected in a study on chicken labelling (Abrams, 2015).

Yet, a common limitation of many empirical studies that evaluate the effect of framing, is the lack of a control group (i.e., Abrams, 2015; Anghelcev et al., 2020; Baum et al., 2021; Shan et al., 2020). These studies provide only insights about the relative effect of loss- and gain-framing, but do not allow to draw a conclusion about the effect of framing versus no framing. Among the few studies which incorporate a control group, different approaches to designing the control information

can be found. First, the control group only received parts of the information, whereas the experimental groups received additional information with the framing (Britwum & Yiannaka, 2019). However, in such a treatment design the groups receive a different extent of information. Second, the control group received a historical account of the phenomenon in question. A study on climate change reporting used a text describing the history of climate change reporting for the control group, whereas the treatment groups received text in the form of newspaper articles (Nabi et al., 2018). Also, here the information provided in the control group is not comparable to the other treatment groups. Third, other research used information irrelevant to the research topic for the control group (Gray & Harrington, 2011; Weingarten & Hartmann, 2023). In this case, the effect of the same information in absence of the specific framing cannot be tested. Lastly, the study by Cucchiara et al. (2015) is an example of a framing experiment where information is provided to the control group in a neutral manner. While respondents in the positive and negative frame group are informed about the health benefits of consuming organic seafood or about the potential detrimental health effect if abstaining from consumption, participants in the neutral frame obtained information on organic certification for seafood. Therefore, the present study tests the effect of framing versus no framing and additionally compares the relative effects of loss- versus gain-framing.

2.3. Video-based communication

When communicating an innovation, developers or marketers not only need to select the appropriate format (i.e. framing), but also the communication medium. While the application of video clips in marketing and communications is prevalent, research studies using video clips as an information tool remain scarce (Bscheiden et al., 2020). For the communication of abstract or complex subject matters, videos were identified as a helpful communication medium (Goldberg et al., 2019; Goodwin et al., 2018; Krantz & Monroe, 2016) and led to stronger effects than text-based communication (Cheung et al., 2017; Goldberg et al., 2019). In text-based communication framing can only be expressed through linguistic features (i.e. words), whereas video-based communications can use also additional means, such as colours, images and animations. For example, gains can be accentuated through different colours, then losses. Red is mostly associated with negativity (Elliot & Maier, 2014), whereas the colour green is often associated with more positive perceptions (Moller et al., 2009). A study on perceived healthiness of products showed that green labels lead to higher health evaluations than red labels with the same information (Schuldt, 2013). Research on loss- and gain-framing combined with colours has demonstrated that participants who were exposed to loss-framing together with red colour elements showed significantly higher behavioural intentions (Gerend & Sias, 2009). The usage of colours in food packaging highlighted that package colour influences the perception of healthiness, which in turn has an effect on purchase intentions (Huang & Lu, 2016). Therefore, the present study utilizes video-based communication instead of text-based communication.

3. The present study

The present study focuses on beneficial soil-microbes, such as bacteria or fungi, as an innovation to improve nutrient use efficiency and pest resistance (Berg, 2009; Chen et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2011). Through these effects, beneficial soil-microbes have the potential to reduce the dependence of agricultural production on chemical fertilizer and plant protection products, thereby contributing to sustainable food production. As the context of application and commercialization is still in development (Lee Díaz et al., 2021), food produced with beneficial soil-microbes are of little relevance in the market yet. In the long-term, the success of this innovation heavily depends on consumers' acceptance. While at present consumers know little about this production

method, the question is how information must be designed to promote a positive assessment.

The objective of the present study is to investigate how framing influences consumers' acceptance of agricultural food innovations at the example of beneficial soil-microbes in tomato production. To conceptualize consumers' acceptance, we investigate consumers' purchase intention of, and their implicit and explicit attitudes towards, tomatoes cultivated with this innovation. As a communication tool, we use video clips. We apply a combination of visual and linguistic framing in the format of short explanatory video clips and consider besides a gain- and a loss-frame also a neutral frame. To disentangle the effect of goal-framing on its own, we created a control video which explains the mechanisms of beneficial soil-microbes, avoiding any framing in the direction of loss- or gain-framing. Thereby, we can elicit the contribution of goal-framing compared to no framing and the relative effects of loss- and gain-framing. We hypothesise that video clips which emphasise consequences of adoption or the lack thereof (loss- and gain-framing) have a stronger effect on: (a) explicit attitudes; (b) implicit attitudes; and (c) purchase intentions than an information video with no specific goal-framing. According to the literature on framing effects, we expect that the effect of loss-framing is stronger compared to gain-framing on both attitude levels as well as on purchase intentions. Furthermore, we hypothesise that the effect of video-based frames on purchase intention is serially mediated by explicit and implicit attitudes. Based on Baum et al. (2021), and Weingarten and Hartmann (2023) we assume that framing significantly influences explicit attitudes, which influences implicit attitudes, which influences intentions. The pre-registration, experimental material, data and analytic script can be viewed here: <https://osf.io/n9xj5>.

4. Material and methods

4.1. Data and design

We conducted an experimental online study with German consumers. The study followed a between-subjects design with three treatment conditions (loss-frame vs. gain-frame vs. no frame). Participants were randomly assigned to one out of the three conditions by watching a video. Recruitment occurred via a market research agency in 2022, and was designed to be representative of the adult population living in Germany with respect to age, gender, education and occupation status. To qualify for participation, respondents had to be regular consumers of tomatoes and had to fulfil technical pre-requisites, such as a device with functioning audio and a keyboard. Non-eligible participants were automatically screened out. All participants who completed the experimental study were reimbursed through a bonus point system of the market research agency.

Sample size was defined according to an a priori power analysis with $G \times$ power (Faul et al., 2009). We calculated the power to detect small effect size ($f^2 = 0.013$) with a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA), a power of $1 - \beta = 0.90$ and an $\alpha = 0.05$. The minimal required sample is $n = 675$. To account for possible exclusions, we decided to recruit approximately 750 participants. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and received ethical approval by the ZEF Research Ethics Committee (certificate number 9_ILR_21).

The online study was programmed using Qualtrics. First, we collected participants' informed consent, assessed screening criteria, and measured socio-demographics. In the second part of the survey, respondents were requested to provide information with respect to their attitudes towards conventionally produced tomatoes and their subjective knowledge about beneficial soil-microbes. Participants who indicated that they had never come across beneficial soil-microbes before, but subsequently had a mean score on the subjective knowledge scale higher than 5 were excluded. Next, participants were requested to watch a short video clip, followed by a video comprehension check based on

three questions about its content. We directly screened out participants who failed to answer these questions correctly. The fourth section of the survey contained the main dependent variable of the study, purchase intentions, and the mediators, implicit and explicit attitudes. The order of the implicit and explicit attitude measure was counterbalanced. The final section of the questionnaire solicited information regarding consumers' organic grocery shopping behaviour and their evaluation of different cultivation methods — conventional, organic and those based on beneficial soil-microbes. After finalizing the survey, participants received a debriefing.

4.2. Video material

Respondents saw one of three video clips, which lasted between 1:43 and 1:55 min. All three clips followed the same structure and explained what beneficial soil-microbes are and how they interact with plants (see OSF folder¹). In all videos the text was read by the same male narrator as a voice-over. To construct the different framing treatments, verbal and visual stimuli were used. For linguistic framing, information was formulated in such a way that it either expressed a gain- or loss-frame while communicating the same meaning. The goal-framed videos described advantages or disadvantages, respectively, which could be gained or lost due to the application of or negligence of beneficial soil-microbes. Those consequences referred to (reducing or preventing) potential harm associated with conventional farming practices with respect to the environment and human health. In contrast, the control group received a video clip with explanations about beneficial soil-microbes and their interaction with the soil and the plant — as did the other groups — however, without explicitly pointing to the positive or negative effects on human health or the environment.

Regarding the visual manipulation, special care was taken to secure the similarity of the images in all three presentations. Visual framing primarily focused on colours to enhance the goal-framing messages where appropriate, with the loss-framing making use of the colour red, the gain-framing of the colour green and the control video applying grey tones. Animations aligned with the loss-framing by elements disappearing and, vice-versa, elements appeared in the gain-framing video. See Table 1 for an example of the applied textual and visual framing cues.

Prior to the main study, we conducted a qualitative ($n = 27$) and a quantitative pre-study ($n = 238$) to test how the videos were perceived, whether the videos were understandable, what participants associated with the videos and whether/what effects the videos had on participants. Based on the findings of the pre-studies, we simplified the design and adjusted some of the information about beneficial soil-microbes.

4.3. Measures

4.3.1. Subjective knowledge

Subjective knowledge about beneficial soil-microbes was measured with four items adapting the short scale of Flynn and Goldsmith (1999). Answers to the four items 'I know quite a lot about beneficial soil-microbes', 'I do not feel very well informed about beneficial soil-microbes', 'Compared to most other people, I know a lot about beneficial soil-microbes', 'When it comes to beneficial soil-microbes, I really don't know much', were captured on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree. The scale had a good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.804$). We used a rescaled mean score (ranging from -3 to +3) of the four items for further analyses. The second and fourth item were reverse coded so that higher values stand for higher subjective knowledge and vice versa.

¹ Control video: <https://osf.io/cjxas>. Gain-framed video: <https://osf.io/56qnd>. Loss-framed video: <https://osf.io/rcux2>.

Table 1

Example of texts and visuals used in the three video clips.

Framing	Narration	Visual
Control	These soil-microbes <u>interact and cooperate</u> with the plant below the soil.	
Loss	Without soil-microbes, the plant as well as the environment and our health are <u>less well protected</u> .	
Gain	Soil-microbes help to <u>better protect</u> the plant as well as the environment and our health.	

Note: The underlined text shows different linguistic cues for framing. Meaning of German text in the videos: Erdmikroben = soil-microbes, Schutz = protection, Gesundheit = health, Umwelt = environment.

4.3.2. Explicit attitude

Explicit attitude towards 'tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes' was measured on a 7-point semantic bipolar scale based on Richetin et al. (2007) — unhealthy–healthy, negative–positive, unattractive–attractive, unpleasant–pleasant, unenjoyable–enjoyable —, and an additional sixth item, bad–good. The construct exhibited excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's α of 0.971). A mean score variable of all six attitude items was created for further analyses, where values ranged from -3 to +3.

The attitude towards 'conventionally produced tomatoes' was measured using the same six items. Construct reliability was as well excellent (Cronbach's α of 0.964).

4.3.3. Implicit attitude

For measuring implicit attitude towards 'tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes' a Single Target-Implicit Association Test (ST-IAT) was used following Bluemke and Fries (2008). In this computer task, the association is measured between a target category, in this case, tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes, and a bipolar outcome category (e.g., negative-positive). The target category was depicted with images of a tomato together with a symbol for microbes. The stimulus words referring to the attribute category positive/negative consisted of the same 12 words used for the explicit attitude measure without positive and negative, namely: unhealthy, healthy, unattractive, attractive, unpleasant, pleasant, unenjoyable, enjoyable, bad and good. The ST-IAT consisted of five blocks (see Table 2) starting with a general practice block in which participant are requested to categorize the stimulus words into one (e.g. positive) or the other (e.g. negative) attribute category. In a second practice block, the target category —tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes — has to be paired additionally with one of the attributes (e.g. positive attribute category). The latter block recurs, which is the first test block. Blocks 2 and 3 are repeated,

Table 2
Description of blocks in the ST-IAT.

Block	Block function	Number of trials	Description	Exemplary process ST-IAT (set: compatible, left) ^a	
				E-key response	I-key response
1	Practice	20	Evaluative words (positive and negative), no tomatoes with microbes	Positive words	Negative words
2	Practice	20	Evaluative words and tomatoes with microbes	Positive words and tomatoes	Negative words
3	Test	74	Evaluative words and tomatoes with microbes, tomatoes switched sides	Positive words	Negative words and tomatoes
4	Practice	20			
5	Test	74			

^a Four randomised ST-IAT order versions/sets were implemented. The four starting positions at block 2 for each set are: (1) tomatoes with beneficial soil-microbes on the right side with positive words (compatible, right), (2) tomatoes with beneficial soil-microbes on the right side with negative words (incompatible, right), (3) tomatoes with beneficial soil-microbes on the left side with positive words (compatible, left), (4) tomatoes with beneficial soil-microbes on the left side with negative words (incompatible, left). Each participant conducted the IAT based on one order/set of blocks.

however, with reversed pairing (e.g. tomatoes with the negative category). Participants needed to assign pictures and words to the correct outcome categories using the ‘E’ and ‘I’ key on their keyboard as quickly as possible. If participants provided a wrong response a red X appeared and they needed to adjust their answer. It is assumed that someone with a positive (negative) implicit attitude towards tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes will find it significantly easier to react to the combination of tomatoes and the positive (negative) category, than to tomatoes and the negative (positive) category on the same side. Taking the difference between the reaction times of the two test blocks provides an indication of the implicit attitude strength. In this study, the differences were calculated using the improved D-score algorithm by Greenwald et al. (2003) with a D-score value of 0 expressing no association and higher (lower) values indicating a positive (negative) association. The internal consistency of the ST-IAT was tested by calculating the Spearman-Brown split-half reliability, which resulted in a good reliability estimate of 0.831. The IAT was programmed using an R script provided by Carpenter et al. (2019). This allowed for an integration of the IAT task in the Qualtrics survey flow.

4.3.4. Purchase intention

Purchase intention of tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes was measured on a 7-point Likert scale (−3 = strongly disagree; +3 = strongly agree) based on the three items intention scale of Fishbein and Ajzen (2010). The statements were formulated in the following way: ‘I intend to purchase tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes’, ‘I plan to purchase tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes’ and ‘I will try to purchase tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes’. The scale yielded an excellent Cronbach’s α of 0.957, which allowed the use of a mean score in the further analysis.

4.4. Data analysis

First, as a randomization check, we tested for differences between all conditions with regard to their socio-demographics, attitude towards ‘conventionally produced tomatoes’ and subjective knowledge about beneficial soil-microbes with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVAs) and chi-square tests. In case of significant differences, we included the variable as covariate in the main analysis. Second, a MANOVA was

conducted with implicit attitude, explicit attitude and purchase intention as dependent variables and framing (control, loss-frame, gain-frame) as the independent variable. Third, using PROCESS model 6 (Hayes, 2018), we tested whether the effect of information framing on purchase intention is serially mediated by implicit attitude and explicit attitude. Bootstrapping was used to obtain bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals of the indirect effects. All analyses were conducted using the statistical computational language R. The R code for the analyses as well as the dataset can be found in the supplementary materials folder on OSF.

5. Results

In total, 759 participants completed the survey. Thirteen participants were excluded, as they encountered technical problems when conducting the ST-IAT or performed the IAT too slowly or too quickly according to the D-score algorithm by Greenwald et al. (2003). One participant was excluded due to inconsistent answers about their subjective knowledge. Thus, the final sample consists of 745 complete observations, with 223 participants being part of the control group, 200 of the loss group, and 322 of the gain group. Differences in group size came about by programmed screen-out criteria after participants watched the videos. Table 3 shows that the final sample (n = 745) reflects the structure of the German population aged 18–65 years old with respect to sociodemographic characteristics very well.

The randomization check revealed no significant difference between the groups concerning socio-demographics and attitude ‘towards conventional tomatoes’ (all p’s > 0.061). Though, subjective knowledge is low in all three groups, significant differences exist between the groups (F(2, 742) = 3.527, p = 0.030, and $\eta_p^2 = 0.009$) with the control group having the highest subjective knowledge ($\bar{X}_{Control} = -1.570$, SD = 1.270), followed by the participants exposed to the gain video ($\bar{X}_{Gain} = -1.784$, SD = 1.289). The loss-frame group revealed the lowest knowledge ($\bar{X}_{Loss} = -1.888$, SD = 1.248). Therefore, we included subjective knowledge as the covariate in the multivariate analysis of

Table 3
Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample and of the German population.

Demographic variable	Category	n	Sample (%)	German population (%) 18–65 years ^a
Gender	Man	355	47.7	48.3
	Woman	389	52.2	51.7
	Non-binary/other	1	0.1	–
Age	18–29	142	19.1	19.8
	30–39	127	17.1	19.4
	40–49	134	18.0	18.0
	50–59	179	24.0	23.7
	60 years and above	163	21.9	19.1
Education	Basic education (still in school/training or general school education)	154	20.6	20.9
	Intermediate (apprenticeship, vocational training, or technical school diploma)	443	59.4	59.4
	Advanced (bachelor’s degree, master’s degree, or doctorate)	148	19.9	19.7
Occupation	Employed	554	74.4	73.9
	Unemployed, social welfare	47	6.3	6.2
	Pension, retirement	35	4.7	4.9
	Other (e.g., in education, stay-at-home-parent)	109	14.6	15.1

^a References on the demographics: Statistics on gender: Statistisches Bundesamt, 2022a; statistics on age: Statistisches Bundesamt, 2022b; statistics on education: Statistisches Bundesamt, 2022c; statistics on occupation: Statistisches Bundesamt, 2020.

covariance (MANCOVA) (section 5.2).

5.1. Construct evaluation

An exploratory factor analysis with oblique rotation was conducted to investigate construct validity. The items representing the constructs purchase intention, explicit attitude towards tomatoes produced with microbes and subjective knowledge were included in the factor analysis. The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin measure representing sample adequacy ranged between 0.641 and 0.950, which indicates a suitable sample size (Williams et al., 2010). The factor structure replicated the intended structure of the constructs. Factor loadings for each item ranged between 0.712 and 0.966; only one reversed item for subjective knowledge scored relatively low, with 0.434. Further descriptive statistics and correlations of the constructs can be found in Table 4. A comparison of the mean scores of the attitude toward conventional tomatoes and the attitude toward tomatoes produced with soil-microbes highlights, that already through the exposure of the control video did participants evaluate the tomatoes produced with soil-microbes quite positively (2.028 out of a scale ranging from -3 to 3) and much higher than the conventional tomatoes. Further, from the mean values it can be seen that for purchase intentions and explicit attitudes the gain group has the highest mean values, followed by the loss group. For implicit attitudes the loss group has the highest average D-score and the gain group the lowest. Subjective knowledge is generally very low, where the control group has the highest mean. The highest significant correlation can be found between explicit attitudes and purchase intentions. Of smaller magnitude are the significant correlations between the explicit attitude and (a) the implicit attitude and (b) the attitude towards tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes, respectively.

5.2. Effect of goal-framing on explicit and implicit attitudes

To test whether the framing (control, loss-frame, gain-frame) had a significant impact on implicit attitude, explicit attitude and purchase intention we conducted a MANOVA. The group comparisons using Pillai's Trace test resulted in non-significant values, with $F(6, 1482) = 1.454, p = 0.191$, and $\eta_p^2 = 0.006$. Table 4 shows that the mean values for purchase intentions as well as explicit attitude are higher in the loss group than the gain group and the control groups; however, these are not significant differences. Implicit attitudes are highest for the loss group, but are then followed by the control group and lowest values can be observed in the gain group.

To rule out that our results have been influenced by differences in subjective knowledge between the treatment groups, we conducted a MANCOVA. We found no significant effect of the covariate subjective knowledge ($F(3, 739) = 0.881, p = 0.451, \eta_p^2 = 0.004$) on the outcome variables, intention, explicit and implicit attitudes. Therefore, subjective knowledge was excluded in the proceeding analysis.

5.3. Mediation analysis

Using PROCESS (model 6; Hayes, 2022), we tested whether implicit and explicit attitude serially mediated the effect of framing on purchase intention. We considered explicit attitude as the first and implicit attitude as the second serial mediator. As the independent variable consists of three categories (control, loss-frame, gain-frame), we followed the recommendations by Hayes and Montoya (2017) to apply Helmert coding. Through Helmert coding we compare the average effect of goal-framing (loss and gain; D_1) relative to the control condition, and the relative effect between the gain and loss group (D_2 ; Hayes, 2018; Hayes & Montoya, 2017). Table 5 provides an illustration of the applied coding scheme. We used bootstrapping (with 10,000 bootstrap samples) to obtain bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals of the indirect effects generated by the independent variable on the dependent variable through the mediator variables.

Results of the serial mediation analysis show that goal-framing compared to no framing has a significant positive effect on explicit attitude ($a_{11} = 0.164, p = 0.043$; see Fig. 1). Hence, the goal-framing group (which received either loss- or gain-framing) showed a positive impact on explicit attitudes in comparison to the group which received the control video. In contrast, no significant difference between gain-versus loss-framing could be observed on the explicit attitude ($a_{12} = 0.036, p = 0.693$). Gain-framing, in addition, led to a significant, more positive implicit attitude compared to loss-framing ($a_{22} = -0.060, p = 0.045$), which implies that gain-framing is superior to loss-framing in influencing implicit attitudes. Albeit, no support was found for a significant effect on the implicit attitude when considering loss- and gain-framing together in comparison to the control video ($a_{21} = -0.013, p = 0.621$). Moreover, the model showed that explicit attitudes were significantly related to implicit attitudes ($d_{21} = 0.029, p = 0.017$) and purchase intentions ($b_1 = 0.775, p = 0.000$), but no relationship between implicit attitudes and purchase intentions was found ($b_2 = -0.022, p = 0.826$).

We analysed the indirect effect to evaluate mediational effects. Table 6 shows that 95 per cent confidence intervals (10,000 bootstrap samples) for all indirect effects include zero. This implies that no mediation effect could be detected. Hence, neither explicit, nor implicit attitudes can causally explain the relationship between information framing and purchase intention.

To single out whether gain- or loss-framing alone has an effect, we also conducted the same serial mediation analysis using indicator coding. Indicator coding allows for the comparison of each experimental condition to the control condition. The results show that neither loss-framing nor gain-framing in comparison to the control video had a significant effect on any of the dependent variables, not on explicit attitudes, on implicit attitudes nor on intentions (see Appendix, Table A1). No indirect effect of the serial mediation could be detected either (see Appendix, Table A2).

Lastly, as pre-registered exploratory analyses, we tested the mediation effect of explicit and implicit attitudes on intentions separately using again Helmert and indicator coding. Therefore, we ran PROCESS mediation model 4 (Hayes, 2018) four times, where the effect of information framing on purchase intentions was mediated either (a) by explicit attitudes or (b) by implicit attitudes. The results mainly reflect the outcomes of the serial mediation analysis with the equivalent coding.² Magnitude of indirect effects as well as significance levels are similar to the results of the main analysis. The effect of goal-framing vs. control was significant on explicit attitudes, and the effect of loss- vs. gain-framing on implicit attitudes. The single mediation analyses using indicator coding did not result in any significant coefficients, except for that of explicit attitudes on intentions. No mediation effect was detected in any of the models.

6. Discussion

This study is one of the first to investigate the effect of information framing using video clips on consumers acceptance. Also, the impact that different information framing has on implicit and explicit attitudes is, to the best of our knowledge, a gap not addressed in literature yet. Our research focused on the effect of information framing on consumers' explicit and implicit attitudes and purchase intentions of tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes. We used short video clips as the communication modality for the information treatments.

6.1. Effects of information framing

The results partly confirmed the first hypothesis. Goal-framing is significantly more effective than no framing in influencing explicit

² For detailed results, see OSF folder: <https://osf.io/rk9wq>.

Table 4

Descriptive statistics and correlation of constructs for attitude towards conventional tomatoes, purchase intentions of, subjective knowledge of and attitude measures of tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes.

		Control group (n = 223)	Gain group (n = 322)	Loss group (n = 200)	Correlation			
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Conv. Tomatoes	Tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes		
					Expl. Attitude	Expl. Attitude	Impl. Attitude	Purchase intentions
Conv. Tomatoes	Expl. Attitude	1.167 (1.286)	1.297 (1.403)	1.120 (1.355)	1			
Tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes	Expl. Attitude	2.028 (1.029)	2.174 (0.989)	2.210 (0.986)	0.264***	1		
	Impl. Attitude	0.247 (0.322)	0.268 (0.335)	0.209 (0.331)	0.045	0.086	1	
	Purchase intentions	1.365 (1.184)	1.527 (1.143)	1.557 (1.224)	0.062	0.660***	0.050	1
	Subjective knowledge	-1.570 (1.270)	-1.784 (1.248)	-1.888 (1.289)	-0.004	-0.033	0.053	-0.016

Note: Explicit attitudes, purchase intention, and subjective knowledge can range between -3 and 3. Pearson correlation coefficients. **, *** indicate a significance level at 5%, and 1%, respectively.

Table 5

Applied Helmert coding.

Group	D ₁	D ₂
Control group	- 2/3	0
Gain group	1/3	- 1/2
Loss group	1/3	1/2

attitudes. This indicates that highlighting the environmental as well as health-related benefits of using (or losses of abstaining from using) beneficial soil-microbes are more effective than neutrally formulated information. These findings are in line with research on offshore wind-energy, where, on average, the no-framing group showed the lowest acceptance for wind-energy compared to the framing groups. As in our study, the control group was presented more general information without highlighting specific benefits (Walker et al., 2014). Also, in research on food products with aesthetical imperfections, goal-framing was more effective than the control treatment in improving preferences; the authors suggest that it is the salience of the framed messages which create stronger effects, and not the framing itself (Lagerkvist et al., 2023). In line with the studies discussed above, our results show that goal-framing impacts the explicit evaluations more than information with no specific framing. However, our analysis could not detect an effect attributed solely to gain- or loss-framing in comparison to the control group. For this particular analysis, the sample size was smaller than that employed in the main analyses, which potentially led to an underpowered test, which lacked the capacity to detect any framing effects.

Contrary to our expectations, the effect of goal-framing could not be

observed for implicit attitudes. According to dual-construct approaches, implicit associations reflect more stable attitudes that are the results of learning processes and socialisation over longer time periods (Gawronski & Bodenhausen, 2006; Greenwald & Banaji, 2017). The impact of information on implicit attitudes in the field of innovations is something that has not been researched to a wide degree yet. Several studies involving information provision about new concepts or products highlight the impact information can have on implicit attitudes; for example, short information cues about various fictious products can impact implicit attitudes towards those products (Ackermann & Palmer, 2014), and serve a mediating role in the effect of information on purchase

Table 6

Relative indirect effects of serial mediation analysis.

	Path	Coeff. (SE)	Lower Limit CI	Upper Limit CI
D ₁ : control vs. goal-framing	D ₁ -> M ₁ ->	-0.000 (0.001)	-0.001	0.001
	M ₂ -> Y	0.127 (0.064)	-0.001	0.252
	D ₁ -> M ₁ -> Y	0.000 (0.003)	-0.005	0.007
D ₂ : gain- vs. loss-framing	D ₂ -> M ₁ ->	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.007	0.001
	M ₂ -> Y	0.028 (0.070)	-0.111	0.162
	D ₂ -> M ₁ -> Y	0.001 (0.006)	-0.012	0.015
	D ₂ -> M ₂ -> Y			

Note: Using 95% confidence interval bootstrapping, 10,000 resamples. Coeff. = coefficients, SE = standard errors, M₁ = explicit attitude; M₂ = implicit attitude; Y = purchase intention.

Fig. 1. Results of the serial mediation analysis.

Note: Results of the serial mediation analysis examining relative effects of video framing on purchase intentions serially mediated by explicit and implicit attitudes. **, *** indicate a significance level at 5%, and 1% respectively, dashed lines indicating insignificant relations.

intentions of cultivated meat (Baum et al., 2021) or the effect of information on attitudes towards genome editing (Nguyen et al., 2022). However, in our study, with the introduction of tomatoes with beneficial soil-microbes, implicit attitudes may have not taken shape yet. Our subjective knowledge measure shows that in all three groups subjective knowledge is rather low (mean scores between -1.57 and -1.89 on a scale from -3 to $+3$). This indicates that there is hardly any past knowledge which may have shaped implicit attitudes before our information treatment. Research has shown that implicit attitudes towards a branded product may be transferred to another product from the same brand, irrespective of the other product's traits (Ratliff et al., 2012). This was also illustrated with attitudes towards individuals by Ranganath and Nosek (2008), who highlight that implicit associations may be transferred from one to another. This holds potential consequences for innovations; a consumer may form implicit attitudes based on another familiar product, which they can relate to the innovation in question. Therefore, for the case of innovations, implicit attitudes towards certain innovations may only be susceptible to information if consumers can base it on a similar concept or category. Nguyen et al. (2022) also come to similar conclusions about GM foods and gene editing, where consumers' implicit evaluation of gene editing may be explained by consumers' evaluation of GM food and aligned information. For the case of cultured meat, the authors also infer that attitudes are transferred from another related category towards the new object in question (Bekker et al., 2017). For the case of beneficial soil-microbes, we believe that at this point, there might be no other concept that consumers may infer or base their implicit attitudes on, which could explain the inconclusive implicit attitudes regarding tomatoes produced with soil-microbes. This poses a question for future research, to investigate to what degree innovations and new concepts can impact implicit attitudes and whether these play a role in the formation of acceptance of innovations in the long term.

Based on prospect theory, the second hypothesis predicted that a loss-frame would lead to a stronger attitudinal change as well as stronger purchase intentions compared to a gain-frame. We found no significant difference between gain- and loss-framing on explicit attitudes nor on purchase intention. One explanation for the absence of an effect might lie in the formulation of the loss-frame. The formulation of losses in a video about the additional use of beneficial soil-microbes resulted in phrases which may have appeared unusual to some participants, although our pre-test indicated that our videos were understandable and clear. Yet, this could have limited the persuasiveness of the loss-framing video.

Contrary to our second hypothesis, we found an opposite effect of gain- and loss-framing on the implicit measures in the mediation analysis. According to our findings, implicit attitudes were more strongly influenced by gain-framing compared to loss-framing. Previous research found a similar pattern in the domain of health behaviour, where gain-framing appeared to be generally more effective than loss-framing (Gallagher & Updegraff, 2012; Gray & Harrington, 2011; O'Keefe & Jensen, 2006, 2007, 2008). A possible explanation for this effect is offered by Cucchiaro et al. (2015). The authors argue that the consumption of organic food can be considered prevention-driven behaviour, and thus part of the health behaviour domain. This suggests that the effect of loss- and gain-framing dealing with certain food-related topics could follow the same pattern as health-related behaviour. Since the video clips in the present study referred to both environmental and health impacts in the goal-framing, the relative persuasiveness of gain- and loss-framing becomes less clearly defined. Thus, the inclusion of these argumentation lines could have interfered with the relative effectiveness of loss- and gain-framing. However, it remains unclear why the effect of the described consequences related to human health might have been detected only in participants' implicit attitudes. This remains a potential research subject for future studies, which may evaluate the effect of gain- and loss-framing related to health behaviour and its effect on implicit attitudes. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, the

effect of goal-framing on implicit attitudes is a research topic that has been hardly addressed so far.

Thirdly, we hypothesized that the effect of information framing on intentions would be serially mediated by both attitudes. Our results did not detect a serial mediation. Nonetheless, regarding the explicit measure, a trend towards the mediation effect could be seen. This indicates that explicit attitudes may play an important role as a single mediator, rather than one mediator with both attitudes in the serial mediation model. In particular, implicit attitudes do not appear to explain purchase intentions. However, as previously discussed, aspects such as the inclusion of health consequences in goal-framing or a lack of implicit attitude formation may have interfered with the implicit attitude measurement.

6.2. Limitations

When interpreting the results, some limitations should be considered. The first limitation concerns the design of the control video. Due to the novelty of the innovation and consumers' lack of knowledge, it was necessary to provide also the control group with information prior to the elicitation of attitudes and intentions. The control video does not contain any framing of gains or losses of applying or not applying the innovation; however, it provides information such as that soil-microbes are useful for the plant, i.e., allowing an adjustment of pesticide applications. The mean values indicate that this already motivated a positive attitude toward tomatoes produced with beneficial soil-microbes (above 2 on a scale from -3 to 3), which was also close to the positive evaluations from the goal-framing groups, and much higher than for conventional tomatoes. This could indicate a ceiling effect (Chyung et al., 2020), meaning that all our participants scored toward the maximum range of our direct measures. This positive effect of the control video could have then impacted the analysis consequentially, as the tests may not have been able to detect the (more) positive effects of the goal-framing. As previously discussed, other studies have used diverse solutions, which shows that there is no sole procedure on how to implement a control condition in research on information framing. Especially when the presented information deals with innovations, which encompass inherently new elements, information provision about the innovation prior to its evaluation is necessary. Yet, with the inclusion of a control video, we were able to elicit the effectiveness of goal-framing in relation to general information provision.

Second, our sample consists of heterogeneous participants, thus the effect of framing may also differ based on different consumer segments (Just & Goddard, 2023). Literature has reported several aspects which could impact the direction and effectiveness of loss- and gain-framing, particularly in health communications (Updegraff & Rothman, 2013). One such aspect is illustrated by the congruence hypothesis; there, it is assumed that personal motivational orientations, such as avoidance and approach orientation, mediate the effect of loss- and gain-framing (Mann et al., 2004). Additional potential mediators include an individual's issue involvement (Rothman et al., 2006) or their need for cognition (Sleboda & Lagerkvist, 2021). In this regard our study is limited, we did not account for those mediators. Future research can consider exploring the effect of information framing for different consumer groups.

Third, because of the research and development stage of beneficial soil-microbes, food products using this technology are not available on the market. Consequently, a hypothetical description of the innovation was used in the videos and only attitudes and the intention to purchase the innovation could be researched.

Fourth, our study only provides a snapshot into hypothetical consumer acceptance. As our results illustrate, it remains unclear to what degree information provision can have a long-term effect on attitudes (in particular on implicit attitudes), intentions and consequently behaviour. Future research dealing with the acceptance of an unknown innovation could benefit from exploring the long-term effect of (repeated)

information provision on attitudes. Yet, our results provide guidelines - on a population level - about how information framing can impact attitudes and behavioural intentions also for other future agricultural technologies.

Fifth, in order to strive for successful adoption of innovations in the future, consumers' acceptance in the form of purchasing behaviour itself has to be investigated. A significant amount of research has addressed the gap between attitudes and behaviour in various domains of behaviour (i.e., ElHaffar et al., 2020; Glasman & Albarracín, 2006; Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002). Therefore, this study remains limited in its potential to provide predictions about future purchasing behaviour; albeit, it provides a first starting point.

Sixth, the actual environmental impact that the acceptance and increased purchase of foods produced with beneficial soil-microbes can induce is contingent on many specific circumstances on the field. The current status of research indicates that beneficial soil-microbes can offer various benefits, which can result in a reduced usage of harmful chemicals by the farmer (Elnahal et al., 2022). However, further research and development is needed for successful long-term applications on agricultural fields and consequently environmental impacts (Lee Díaz et al., 2021).

Lastly, we could not detect any effects of gain- or loss-framing individually in comparison to the control group; albeit, this may be attributed to sample size. Nonetheless, this issue should be taken up in future research.

6.3. Implications

Looking ahead, a transition towards more sustainable food production will require changes and the implementation of innovations on the field. To ensure success, all stakeholders should be considered in such a process. In order to foster transparency in food production processes and the acceptance thereof, communication campaigns about such processes or changes are necessary. Consumer attitudes with regard to innovations such as beneficial soil-microbes will, in many instances, be influenced by available information. Therefore, effective information provision is essential to ensure innovation acceptance by a wide range of stakeholders. With regard to the construction of communication approaches, we have taken a step towards the usage of visual and linguistic framing. Plenty of communication targeted at consumers uses video clips as their communication modality, thus our insights line up with such popular means of communication. This may entail outreach communication about sustainability programs, such as the Farm-to-Fork strategy by the European Union or the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), which both specifically address changes at the agricultural level. Also, retailers or producers who intend to inform their consumers about innovative products with new production methods may consider our results when designing communication campaigns.

7. Conclusion

Many scientists have highlighted the extensive impact that agricultural and food production create with regard to the environment. Thus, there is a call and urgency to change production processes in the food

Appendix

Table A.1
Relative effects of serial mediation analysis using indicator coding, $n = 745$.

	M ₁ : Expl. Attitudes	M ₂ : Impl. Attitudes	Y: Intention
	Coeff. (SE)	Coeff. (SE)	Coeff (SE)
D ₁ : gain-framing vs. control	a ₁₁ : 0.146 (0.087)	a ₂₁ : 0.017 (0.029)	c' ₁ : 0.050 (0.078)
D ₂ : loss-framing vs. control	a ₁₂ : 0.182 (0.097)	a ₂₂ : -0.043 (0.032)	c' ₂ : 0.050 (0.087)

(continued on next page)

value chain, which is also reflected in various programs at the European level. To support this process, beneficial soil-microbes have been recognized as a potential tool for more sustainable agriculture. Our study investigated whether different information framing can contribute to fostering consumer acceptance of beneficial soil-microbes. According to our findings neither explicit, nor implicit attitudes can causally explain the relationship between information framing and purchase intention. However, the results indicate that communication about innovations with goal-framing has a positive effect on explicit attitudes. The frames individually (gain- or loss-framing) did not appear to be effective on their own. Video clips that illustrate environment- and health-related consequences of innovation application turned out to be more persuasive than a video with a general description of beneficial soil-microbes. The findings on implicit attitudes remain somewhat inconclusive. Our results suggest that loss- and gain-framing is not as effective as theory suggests when consumers are confronted with unknown innovations in food production. In particular, our evaluation of different notions of attitudes has shown the complexity of attitude formation; which could imply that one-time information provision might not be sufficient to impact consumer attitudes and acceptance toward innovations. Future research and communications may build on these insights.

CRedit author statement

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data statement

Data is available via the Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/n9xj5>

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Table A.1 (continued)

	M ₁ : Expl. Attitudes	M ₂ : Impl. Attitudes	Y: Intention
	Coeff. (SE)	Coeff. (SE)	Coeff (SE)
M ₁	–	d ₂₁ : 0.029 (0.012) **	b ₁ : 0.775 (0.033) ***
M ₂	–	–	b ₂ : –0.022 (0.099)

Note: Using 95% confidence interval bootstrapping, 10,000 resamples. Coeff. = coefficients, SE = standard errors, M₁ = explicit attitude; M₂ = implicit attitude; Y = purchase intention. **, *** indicate a significance level at 5%, and 1%, respectively.

Table A.2

Relative indirect effects of serial mediation analysis (using indicator coding).

	Path	Coeff. (SE)	Lower Limit CI	Upper Limit CI
D₁: gain-framing vs. control	D ₁ -> M ₁ -> M ₂ -> Y	–0.000 (0.000)	–0.001	0.001
	D ₁ -> M ₁ -> Y	0.113 (0.069)	–0.020	0.250
	D ₁ -> M ₂ -> Y	–0.000 (0.003)	–0.008	0.007
D₂: loss-framing vs. control	D ₂ -> M ₁ -> M ₂ -> Y	–0.000 (0.000)	–0.002	0.001
	D ₂ -> M ₁ -> Y	0.141 (0.077)	–0.012	0.289
	D ₂ -> M ₂ -> Y	0.001 (0.005)	–0.009	0.013

Note: Using 95% confidence interval bootstrapping, 10,000 resamples. Coeff. = coefficients, SE = standard errors, M₁ = explicit attitude; M₂ = implicit attitude; Y = purchase intention.

References

Abrams, K. M. (2015). Loss aversion and regulatory focus effects in the absence of numbers: Qualitatively framing equivalent messages on food labels. *Journal of Applied Communications*, 99(3), 21–36. <https://doi.org/10.4148/1051-0834.1054>

Ackermann, C.-L., & Palmer, A. (2014). The contribution of implicit cognition to the theory of reasoned action model: A study of food preferences. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 30(5–6), 529–550. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2013.877956>

Ackermann, C.-L., Teichert, T., & Truong, Y. (2018). ‘So, what is it? And do I like it?’ New product categorisation and the formation of consumer implicit attitude. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 34(9–10), 796–818. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0267257X.2018.1515102>

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)

Anghelcev, G., McGroarty, S., Sar, S., Moultrie, J. L., & Huang, Y. (2020). Marketing processed organic foods: The impact of promotional message framing (vice vs. Virtue advertising) on perceptions of healthfulness. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 26(6), 401–424. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2020.1792022>

Baum, C. M., Bröring, S., & Lagerkvist, C.-J. (2021). Information, attitudes, and consumer evaluations of cultivated meat. *Food Quality and Preference*, 92(6), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2021.104226>

Bekker, G. A., Fischer, A. R. H., Tobi, H., & van Trijp, H. C. M. (2017). Explicit and implicit attitude toward an emerging food technology: The case of cultured meat. *Appetite*, 108, 245–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2016.10.002>

Berg, G. (2009). Plant-microbe interactions promoting plant growth and health: Perspectives for controlled use of microorganisms in agriculture. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 84(1), 11–18. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-009-2092-7>

Bluemke, M., & Friese, M. (2008). Reliability and validity of the single-target IAT (ST-IAT): Assessing automatic affect towards multiple attitude objects. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 38(6), 977–997. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.487>

Britwum, K., & Yiannaka, A. (2019). Consumer willingness to pay for food safety interventions: The role of message framing and issue involvement. *Food Policy*, 86(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2019.05.009>

Bschaden, A., Mandarano, E., & Stroebel-Benschop, N. (2020). Effects of a documentary on consumer perception of the environmental impact of meat consumption. *British Food Journal*, 123(1), 177–189. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-02-2020-0138>

Carpenter, T. P., Pogacar, R., Pullig, C., Kouril, M., Aguilar, S., LaBouff, J., Isenberg, N., & Chakroff, A. (2019). Survey-software implicit association tests: A methodological and empirical analysis. *Behavior Research Methods*, 51(5), 2194–2208. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13428-019-01293-3>

Chen, M., Arato, M., Borghi, L., Nouri, E., & Reinhardt, D. (2018). Beneficial services of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi - from ecology to application. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2018.01270>

Cheung, K. L., Schwabe, I., Walthouwer, M. J. L., Oenema, A., Lechner, L., & Vries, H. de (2017). Effectiveness of a video-versus text-based computer-tailored intervention for obesity prevention after one year: a randomized controlled trial. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(10), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jypmed.2015.11.002>

Chyng, S. Y., Hutchinson, D., & Shamsy, J. A. (2020). Evidence-based survey design: Ceiling effects associated with response scales. *Performance Improvement*, 59(6), 6–13. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pfi.21920>

Cucchiara, C., Kwon, S., & Ha, S. (2015). Message framing and consumer responses to organic seafood labeling. *British Food Journal*, 117(5), 1547–1563. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-07-2014-0261>

Eagly, A. H., & Chaiken, S. (1993). *The psychology of attitudes*. Harcourt brace Jovanovich college publishers.

ElHaffar, G., Durif, F., & Dubé, L. (2020). Towards closing the attitude-intention-behavior gap in green consumption: A narrative review of the literature and an overview of future research directions. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 275, Article 122556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122556>

Elliot, A. J., & Maier, M. A. (2014). Color psychology: Effects of perceiving color on psychological functioning in humans. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 65, 95–120. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010213-115035>

Elnahal, A. S. M., El-Saadony, M. T., Saad, A. M., Desoky, E.-S. M., El-Tahan, A. M., Rady, M. M., AbuQamar, S. F., & El-Tarabily, K. A. (2022). The use of microbial inoculants for biological control, plant growth promotion, and sustainable agriculture: A review. *European Journal of Plant Pathology*, 162(4), 759–792. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10658-021-02393-7>

Entman, R. M. (1993). Framing: Towards clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1993.tb01304.x>

European Commission. (2019). *Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions - The European Green Deal, COM, 2019) 640 final* (2019).

European Union. (2020). *Farm to Fork Strategy: For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system*.

Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Buchner, A., & Lang, A.-G. (2009). Statistical power analyses using G*Power 3.1: Tests for correlation and regression analyses. *Behavior Research Methods*, 41(4), 1149–1160. <https://doi.org/10.3758/BRM.41.4.1149>

Fishbein, M., & Ajzen, I. (2010). *Predicting and changing behavior: The reasoned action approach*. Psychology Press.

Flynn, L. R., & Goldsmith, R. E. (1999). A short, reliable measure of subjective knowledge. *Journal of Business Research*, 46, 57–66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(98\)00057-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(98)00057-5)

Gallagher, K. M., & Updegraff, J. A. (2012). Health message framing effects on attitudes, intentions, and behavior: A meta-analytic review. *Annals of Behavioral Medicine*, 43(1), 101–116. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12160-011-9308-7>

Gawronski, B., & Bodenhausen, G. V. (2006). Associative and propositional processes in evaluation: An integrative review of implicit and explicit attitude change. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132(5), 692–731. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.132.5.692>

Gerend, M. A., & Sias, T. (2009). Message framing and color priming: How subtle threat cues affect persuasion. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 45(4), 999–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2009.04.002>

Glasman, L. R., & Albarracín, D. (2006). Forming attitudes that predict future behavior: A meta-analysis of the attitude-behavior relation. *Psychological Bulletin*, 132(5), 778–822. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.132.5.778>

Goldberg, M. H., van der Linden, S., Ballew, M. T., Rosenthal, S. A., Gustafson, A., & Leiserowitz, A. (2019). The experience of consensus: Video as an effective medium to communicate scientific agreement on climate change. *Science Communication*, 41(5), 659–673. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547019874361>

Goodwin, D., Raffin, M., Jeffrey, P., & Smith, H. M. (2018). Informing public attitudes to non-potable water reuse - the impact of message framing. *Water Research*, 145, 125–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.08.006>

Gray, J. B., & Harrington, N. G. (2011). Narrative and framing: A test of an integrated message strategy in the exercise context. *Journal of Health Communication*, 16(3), 264–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730.2010.529490>

Greenwald, A. G., & Banaji, M. R. (1995). Implicit social cognition: Attitudes, self-esteem, and stereotypes. *Psychological Review*, 102(1), 4–27. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.102.1.4>

- Greenwald, A. G., & Banaji, M. R. (2017). The implicit revolution: Reconceiving the relation between conscious and unconscious. *American Psychologist*, 72(9), 861–871. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000238>
- Greenwald, A. G., & Lai, C. K. (2020). Implicit social cognition. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 71, 419–445. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-010419-050837>
- Greenwald, A. G., McGhee, D. E., & Schwartz, J. L. K. (1998). Measuring individual differences in implicit cognition: The implicit association test. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 74(6), 1464–1480. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.74.6.1464>
- Greenwald, A. G., Nosek, B. A., & Banaji, M. R. (2003). Understanding and using the implicit association test: I. An improved scoring algorithm. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 85(2), 197–216. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.85.2.197>
- Hamid, B., Zaman, M., Farooq, S., Fatima, S., Sayyed, R. Z., Baba, Z. A., Sheikh, T. A., Reddy, M. S., El Enshasy, H., Gafur, A., & Suriani, N. L. (2021). Bacterial plant biostimulants: A sustainable way towards improving growth, productivity, and health of crops. *Sustainability*, 13(5), 2856. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052856>
- Hayes, A. F. (2018). Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach. In *Methodology in the social sciences* (2nd ed.). Guilford Press.
- Hayes, A. F. (2022). Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis. In *A regression-based approach* (3rd ed.). Guilford Press. Third edition.
- Hayes, A. F., & Montoya, A. K. (2017). A tutorial on testing, visualizing, and probing an interaction involving a multicategorical variable in linear regression analysis. *Communication Methods and Measures*, 11(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19312458.2016.1271116>
- Heiman, A., & Zilberman, D. (2011). The effects of framing on consumers' choice of GM foods. *AgBioforum*, 14(3), 171–179.
- Hess, S., Lagerkvist, C. J., Redekop, W., & Pakseresht, A. (2016). Consumers' evaluation of biotechnologically modified food products: New evidence from a meta-survey. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 43(5), 703–736. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbw011>
- Homar, A. R., & Cvelbar, L. K. (2021). The effects of framing on environmental decisions: A systematic literature review. *Ecological Economics*, 183, Article 106950. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.106950>
- Huang, L., & Lu, J. (2016). The impact of package color and the nutrition content labels on the perception of food healthiness and purchase intention. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 22(2), 191–218. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2014.1000434>
- Jeong, Y., & Lundy, L. K. (2015). Evaluating food labels and food messages: An experimental study of the impact of message format and product type on evaluations of magazine food advertisements. *Journal of Applied Communications*, 99(1), 52–66. <https://doi.org/10.4148/1051-0834.1040>
- Just, D. R., & Goddard, J. M. (2023). Behavioral framing and consumer acceptance of new food technologies: Factors influencing consumer demand for active packaging. *Agribusiness*, 39(1), 3–27.
- Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1979). Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. *Econometrica*, 47(2), 263–292. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1914185>
- Kamrath, C., Wesana, J., Bröring, S., & Steur, H. (2019). What do we know about chain actors' evaluation of new food technologies? A systematic review of consumer and farmer studies. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 18(3), 798–816. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12442>
- Kollmuss, A., & Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the Gap: Why do people act environmentally and what are the barriers to pro-environmental behavior? *Environmental Education Research*, 8(3), 239–260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504620220145401>
- Krantz, S. A., & Monroe, M. C. (2016). Message framing matters: Communicating climate change with forest landowners. *Journal of Forestry*, 114(2), 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.5849/jof.14-057>
- Lagerkvist, C. J., Edenbrandt, A. K., Bolos, L. A., & Nayga, R. M. (2023). Consumer acceptance of aesthetically imperfect vegetables – the role of information framing and personal values: Evidence from the United States. *Food Quality and Preference*, 104, Article 104737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2022.104737>
- Lee Diaz, A. S., Macheda, D., Saha, H., Ploll, U., Orine, D., & Biere, A. (2021). Tackling the context-dependency of microbial-induced resistance. *Agronomy*, 11(7), 1293. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy11071293>
- Levin, I. P., Schneider, S. L., & Gaeth, G. J. (1998). All frames are not created equal: A typology and critical analysis of framing effects. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 76(2), 149–188.
- Li, N., & Su, L. Y.-F. (2018). Message framing and climate change communication: A meta-analytical review. *Journal of Applied Communications*, 102(3), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.4148/1051-0834.2189>
- Mann, T., Sherman, D., & Updegraff, J. (2004). Dispositional motivations and message framing: A test of the congruency hypothesis in college students. *Health Psychology: Official journal of the division of health psychology. American Psychological Association*, 23(3), 330–334. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0278-6133.23.3.330>
- Moller, A. C., Elliot, A. J., & Maier, M. A. (2009). Basic hue-meaning associations. *Emotion*, 9(6), 898–902. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0017811>
- van de Mortel, T. F. (2008). Faking it: Social desirability response bias in self-report research. *Australian Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 25(4), 40–48.
- Nabi, R. L., Gustafson, A., & Jensen, R. (2018). Framing climate change: Exploring the role of emotion in generating advocacy behavior. *Science Communication*, 40(4), 442–468. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107554701877601>
- Nguyen, T. H., Ben Taieb, S., Moritaka, M., & Fukuda, S. (2022). Implicit and explicit attitudes toward foods derived from genome editing and genetic modification technologies under different information treatments. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 28(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2022.2037487>
- O'Keefe, D. J., & Jensen, J. D. (2006). The advantages of compliance or the disadvantages of noncompliance? A meta-analytic review of the relative persuasive effectiveness of gain-framed and loss-framed messages. *Annals of the International Communication Association*, 30(1), 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23808985.2006.11679054>
- O'Keefe, D. J., & Jensen, J. D. (2007). The relative persuasiveness of gain-framed and loss-framed messages for encouraging disease prevention behaviors: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of Health Communication*, 12(7), 623–644. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10810730701615198>
- O'Keefe, D. J., & Jensen, J. D. (2008). Do loss-framed persuasive messages engender greater message processing than do gain-framed messages? A meta-analytic review. *Communication Studies*, 59(1), 51–67. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10510970701849388>
- O'Keefe, D. J., & Jensen, J. D. (2006). The advantages of compliance or the disadvantages of noncompliance? A meta-analytic review of the relative persuasive effectiveness of gain-framed and loss-framed messages. *Annals of the International Communication Association*, 30(1), 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23808985.2006.11679054>
- Perrin, J. L. (2011). Emotional responses to environmental messages and future behavioral intentions. *Applied Environmental Education and Communication*, 10(3), 146–157. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1533015X.2011.603612>
- Perugini, M. (2005). Predictive models of implicit and explicit attitudes. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 44(Pt 1), 29–45. <https://doi.org/10.1348/014466604X23491>
- Petty, R. E., & Cacioppo, J. T. (1986). The elaboration likelihood model of persuasion. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 19, 123–205. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60214-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60214-2)
- Ranganath, K. A., & Nosek, B. A. (2008). Implicit attitude generalization occurs immediately; explicit attitude generalization takes time. *Psychological Science*, 19(3), 249–254. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9280.2008.02076.x>
- Ratliif, K. A., Howell, J. L., & Redford, L. (2017). Attitudes toward the prototypical environmentalist predict environmentally friendly behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 51, 132–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2017.03.009>
- Ratliif, K. A., Swinkels, B. A. P., Klerx, K., & Nosek, B. A. (2012). Does one bad apple (juice) spoil the bunch? Implicit attitudes toward one product transfer to other products by the same brand. *Psychology and Marketing*, 29(8), 531–540. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.20540>
- Richetin, J., Perugini, M., Prestwich, A., & O'Gorman, R. (2007). The IAT as a predictor of food choice: The case of fruits versus snacks. *International Journal of Psychology*, 42(3), 166–173. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207590601067078>
- Risius, A., & Hamm, U. (2017). The effect of information on beef husbandry systems on consumers' preferences and willingness to pay. *Meat Science*, 124, 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2016.10.008>
- Römer, U., Schaak, H., & Mußhoff, O. (2019). The perception of crop protection: Explicit vs. implicit association of the public and in agriculture. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 66(11), Article 101346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2019.101346>
- Rothman, A. J., Bartels, R. D., Wlaschin, J., & Salovey, P. (2006). The strategic use of gain- and loss-framed messages to promote healthy behavior: How theory can inform practice. *Journal of Communication*, 56(suppl.1), S202–S220. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2006.00290.x>
- Rothman, A. J., & Salovey, P. (1997). Shaping perceptions to motivate healthy behavior: The role of message framing. *Psychological Bulletin*, 121(1), 3–19. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.121.1.3>
- Rouphael, Y., & Colla, G. (2020). Toward a sustainable agriculture through plant biostimulants: From experimental data to practical applications. *Agronomy*, 10(10), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy10101461>
- Schuld, J. P. (2013). Does green mean healthy? Nutrition label color affects perceptions of healthfulness. *Health Communication*, 28(8), 814–821. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2012.725270>
- Shan, L., Diao, H., & Wu, L. (2020). Influence of the framing effect, anchoring effect, and knowledge on consumers' attitude and purchase intention of organic food. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.02022>
- Singh, J. S., Pandey, V. C., & Singh, D. P. (2011). Efficient soil microorganisms: A new dimension for sustainable agriculture and environmental development. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 140(3–4), 339–353. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2011.01.017>
- Slebođa, P., & Lagerkvist, C. J. (2021). The inverse relation between risks and benefits: The impact of individual differences in information processing style. *PLoS One*, 16(8), Article e0255569. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0255569>
- Statistisches Bundesamt. (2020). Bevölkerung und Erwerbstätigkeit Haushalte und Familien Ergebnisse des Mikrozensus. *Fachserie, I. Reihe* 3.
- Statistisches Bundesamt. (2022a). Bevölkerung (zensus), deutschland, stichtag, geschlecht, altergruppen. Retrieved from <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online?operation=abruftabelleBearbeiten&levelindex=2&levelid=1633496372939&auswahloperation=abruftabelleAuspraegungAuswahlen&auswahlverzeichnis=ordnungsstruktur&auswahlziel=werteabruf&code=12111-0004&auswahltext=werteabruf=starthen#abreadcrum>
- Statistisches Bundesamt. (2022b). Bevölkerung (zensus), deutschland, stichtag, altersjahre. Retrieved from <https://www-genesis.destatis.de/genesis/online?operation=abruftabelleBearbeiten&levelindex=1&levelid=1633493787026&auswahloperation=abruftabelleAuspraegungAuswahlen&auswahlverzeichnis=ordnungsstruktur&auswahlziel=werteabruf&code=12411-0005&auswahltext=werteabruf=starthen#abreadcrum>
- Statistisches Bundesamt. (2022c). Bildungstand. *Bildungsstand, inhalt.html*. (Accessed 14 January 2022).

- Sutherland, C., Sim, C., Gleim, S., & Smyth, S. J. (2020). Canadian consumer insights on agriculture: Addressing the knowledge-gap. *Journal of Agricultural & Food Information*, 21(1–2), 50–72. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496505.2020.1724114>
- Updegraff, J. A., & Rothman, A. J. (2013). Health message framing: Moderators, mediators, and mysteries. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 7(9), 668–679. <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12056>
- Walker, B. J., Wiersma, B., & Bailey, E. (2014). Community benefits, framing and the social acceptance of offshore wind farms: An experimental study in England. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 3, 46–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2014.07.003>
- Weingarten, N., & Hartmann, M. (2023). Let's talk about straw: The effect of information provision on consumers' attitudes towards pig husbandry systems. *British Food Journal*, 125(5), 1840–1853. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-03-2022-0299>
- Whitfield, M., & Jordan, C. H. (2009). Mutual influence of implicit and explicit attitudes. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 45(4), 748–759. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2009.04.006>
- Williams, B., Onsmann, A., & Brown, T. (2010). Exploratory factor analysis: A five-step guide for novices. *Journal of Emergency Primary Health Care*, 8(3), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.33151/ajp.8.3.93wil>